

LandSense

A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

Deliverable 5.4

Quality evaluation of citizen-observed data to the LandSense demonstration cases

Horizon 2020
European Union funding
for Research & Innovation

This project has received funding from the European Union's
Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
under grant agreement No.689812

Project acronym:	LandSense
Project title:	A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring
Project number:	689812
Instrument:	Horizon 2020
Call identifier:	SC5-17-2015
Topic	Demonstrating the concept of citizen observatories
Type of action	Innovation action

Start date of project:	01-09-2016
Duration:	48 months

Deliverable number	D5.4
Deliverable title	LandSense – D5.4: Quality evaluation of citizen-observed data to the LandSense demonstration cases
Deliverable due date	21-12-2018
Lead beneficiary	UNOTT
Work package	5
Deliverable type	Report
Submission date:	20-03-2019
Revision:	Version 1.0

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Title:
Definition of citizen-observed and authoritative data collection requirements for LandSense demonstration cases
Author(s)/Organisation(s):
Julian Rosser UNOTT, Michael Schultz UHEI
Contributor(s):
Giles Foody, Ana-Maria Raimond, Sofia Capellan, Vladimir Mrkajic, Sam Meek, Inian Moorty, Karin Wannemacher and Steffen Fritz

Short Description:
This deliverable reports on the use of the quality assurance (QA) service, developed as part of WP5, to analyse data collected by the LandSense demonstrator pilot case studies. It describes data acquired by the pilots and the preliminary analysis that results from processing the data using the QA service. Assessments of data quality relating to user-captured photographs, ensuring GDPR compliance on user captured photographs, assessing point and polygon field observations, calculating categorical accuracy of classifications of Earth Observation data, and contributor agreement measures are described.
Keywords:
Quality, Volunteer Geographic Information, LandSense, WP5, image quality, polygon topology, user privacy, categorical accuracy, thematic accuracy, citizen science, position accuracy, contributor agreement, EU

History:				
Version	Author(s)	Status	Comment	Date
0.1	Michael Schultz			
	Draft	Initial structure	10.12.2018	
0.2	Julian Rosser and Giles Foody	Draft	Structure, text, photograph validity elements and context information	18.12.2018
0.3	Michael Schultz	Draft	Graphs, overview table, change assessment	19.12.2018
0.4	Giles Foody	Draft	Revisions and recommendations	20.12.2018
0.5	Julian Rosser	Draft	Final draft write up	21.12.2018
0.6	Michael Schultz	Draft	Content revisions	18.02.2019
0.7	Giles Foody	Draft	Language revisions and content	19.02.2019
0.8	Ana-Maria Raimond	Draft	Language revisions and content	22.02.2019
0.9	Michael Schultz	Draft	Revisions and recommendations	06.03.2019
1.0	Julian Rosser	Draft	Edit	20.03.2019

Review:			
Version	Reviewer	Comment	Date
1.01	Linda See	Reviewed the document and made minor editorial changes	21.03.2019

Table of Contents

Summary	8
1 Introduction.....	8
2 Quality evaluation of data collected from the pilot projects	9
2.1 UHEI-OSMlanduse validation	13
2.1.1 Heidelberg, Toulouse and Vienna osmlanduse.org accuracies	14
2.1.2 Geneva osmlanduse.org accuracy and contributor agreement.....	18
2.2 UBA - CityOases (formerly Frei.Raum.Netz).....	20
2.2.1 Results of the face detection analysis	21
2.2.2 Results of the photograph blur analysis	22
2.2.3 Results of the contributor agreement	23
2.3 City of Toulouse – Land Use Change Validation	24
2.3.1 Results of the accuracy analysis	25
2.3.2 Results of the contributor agreement	27
2.4 Serbia – CropSupport.....	28
2.4.1 Results of the photograph analysis	29
2.4.2 Results of the polygon topology check.....	32
2.5 Spain and Indonesia - Natura Alert app.....	33
2.5.1 Authorization.....	33
2.5.2 Data - Query of Birdlife API using GraphQL	33
2.5.3 Reference data for deforestation alerts	34
2.5.4 Results of the accuracy analysis	38
3 Conclusions.....	38
4 Recommendations.....	38
5 References.....	39

List of Figures

Figure 1 Software architecture of the QA-Platform system.....	9
Figure 2 OSMLanduse (UHEI) pilot data dependencies and QA applications, *legend construction of land use is flexible; it is currently CORINE; ** Currently Landsat and Sentinel 2 are used; very high resolution (VHR) data are envisioned.....	13
Figure 3 Outline of reference points (sampling design) for osmlanduse.org (UHEI pilot) pilot cities H = Heidelberg, T = Toulouse and V = Vienna; *Artificial, non-agricultural vegetated areas	15
Figure 4 Class accuracies and confidence intervals for UHEI pilot osmlanduse.org land use reference data consisting of 1482 samples for Heidelberg (H) overall accuracy 87%±1.6%, 1245 for Toulouse (T) overall accuracy 54%±2.7% and 1554 for Vienna (V) overall accuracy 62%±2.3%. *Artificial, non-agricultural vegetated areas	17
Figure 5 Area bias of class accuracies for Heidelberg (H), Toulouse (T) and Vienna (V) *Artificial, non-agricultural vegetated areas. Positive area bias indicates that errors produced by overestimation are higher than by underestimation.	18
Figure 6 Geneva validation campaign contributor agreement among 150 reference points, each inspected by 5 different interpreters; top facets show individual contributor agreement; bottom left indicates match of reference data (UHEI pilot) and osmlanduse.org and bottom right shows locations where osmlanduse.org agreed with the reference data and Scott's Pi was above 0.6 (i.e., substantial agreement).	19
Figure 7 CityOases (UBA) pilot data dependencies and QA applications	20
Figure 8 CityOases guided campaign locations (Quest points) and visited locations (Vienna test case points). Base map copyright: 2018 Microsoft Corporation. 2018 Digital Globe CNES (2018). Distribution Airbus DS 2018.....	21
Figure 9 Example of user photographs from the CityOases pilot submitted and returned by face detection service.....	21
Figure 10 Example of a user photograph from the CityOases pilot with blur applied to the face locations	22
Figure 11 Example image collected by the CityOases pilot (Laplace transform variance = 1420). This image does not score highly due to a relative lack of edges arising from the poor illumination.....	22
Figure 12 Histogram of the Laplace transform variance for 135 City Oases Vienna photographs.....	23
Figure 13 Visited locations and count of revisit for UBA pilot.....	24
Figure 14. IGN Toulouse pilot data showing contributor validated points of change detected using the LACO-Wiki web-based tool. Base map copyright: 2018 French Geoportal.....	25
Figure 15 Class accuracies using reference data consisting of valid (224) samples for Toulouse, with an overall accuracy of 48% ± 5%.	26
Figure 16 Class accuracies for the land use reference data consisting of 190 samples for changes identified by the LandSense Change Detector Service (CDS) as of May 2018. The confidence intervals of the class	

infrastructure(2) exceeded the plotting margins and are thus not shown. The overall accuracy is $46\% \pm 10\%$ ($\alpha = 0.95$)..... 26

Figure 17 Locations of change and the number of times visited for the Toulouse pilot 27

Figure 18 The Toulouse validation campaign contributor agreement among 401 reference points, each inspected by 2 different interpreters; top two sub-figures show individual contributor agreement; bottom left indicates match of reference data and LandSense Change Detector Service; bottom right shows locations where the LandSense Change Detector Service agreed with the reference data and Scott’s PI was above 0.8 (perfect agreement)..... 28

Figure 19 InoSens CropSupport pilot data consisting of user collected points based on mobile device position, digitised polygons of field boundaries, and land parcel boundaries. Base map copyright: 2018 Microsoft Corporation. 2018 Digital Globe CNES (2018). Distribution Airbus DS 2018..... 29

Figure 20 Example of CropSupport images evaluated with the photograph blur checking tool. Variance = 814 (left). Variance = 671 (right)..... 30

Figure 21 Example CropSupport images evaluated with the photograph blur checking tool. Variance = 7784 (left) 30

Figure 22 Histogram of the Laplace transform variance for 113 photographs 31

Figure 23 Example CropSupport image where Laplace transform variance is -8040..... 31

Figure 24 Map of identified overlaps in InoSens CropSupport user polygons. Base map copyright: 2018 Microsoft Corporation. 2018 Digital Globe CNES (2018). Distribution Airbus DS 2018. 32

Figure 25 Overview of the processing steps related to deforestation alerts. *cc = cloud cover; **observation frequency >30 and application of a forest mask..... 35

Figure 26 Binary generalized linear models and the identification of the magnitude thresholds for deforestation detection based on 571 reference points (Devries et al., 2015; Schultz et al., 2018) 37

Figure 27 Red areas show hot spots of detected deforestation. Sub-figures A-F show deforestation patterns at a pixel level 37

Figure 28 Estimated deforestation detection accuracy based on 571 reference points for each tile; whiskers show confidence interval based on Card (1982)..... 38

List of Tables

Table 1 interpretation of Scott’s PI (Sim and Wright, 2005)	11
Table 2 LandSense data quality analysis adapted from D5.2 Data Capture Requirements framework. “T” denotes a QA tested in this report. “A” denotes the test is applicable but not evaluated within this particular work. “–” denotes that the test is not applicable to the current pilot usage or the existing data captured by the pilot. * LandSense Change detector service involvement.	12
Table 3 Class proportions and sampling population for Heidelberg pilot validation campaigns.....	14
Table 4 Frequency of Scott’s PI for four different categories	20
Table 5 Frequency of Scott’s PI for four different categories in the IGN Toulouse campaign.....	25

Abbreviations

Amtliche Topographisch-Kartographische Informationssystem (**ATKIS**)

City of Heidelberg (**CHEI**)

Volunteered geographic information (**VGI**)

European Union (**EU**)

Citizen Observatory Web (**COBWEB**)

General Data Protection Regulations (**GDPR**)

Birdlife International (**BLI**)

Normalized difference moisture index (**NDMI**)

OpenStreetMap (**OSM**)

Vegetation index (**VI**)

University of Heidelberg (**UHEI**)

Umwelbundesamt Vienna (**UBA**)

Amsterdam University (**VU**)

Nottingham University (**UNOTT**)

Institut National de l’Information Géographique et Forestière (**IGN**)

Summary

Volunteered geographic information (VGI) acquired via crowdsourcing has the potential to revolutionise many aspects of science (e.g., citizen science contributions to astronomy) and everyday life (e.g., location based services). The use of VGI is, however, often limited by concerns over its quality, and hence, quality assessment is an important topic (Goodchild and Li, 2012; Antoniou and Skopeliti, 2015; Fonte et al., 2015; Senaratne et al., 2017). VGI data quality is recognised as important within the LandSense project and is the core focus of work package 5 (WP5). Work within this work package has included a review of the literature (deliverable D.5.1), an assessment of the needs of the LandSense pilots (deliverable D.5.2) and, building on the foundations of the EU-funded COBWEB project, the development of a service for quality assessment (deliverable D.5.3). This deliverable reports on the initial application of the LandSense quality assurance service to data collected from campaigns from different pilots carried out in the LandSense pilots (WP4). It will help drive future work to develop and refine the tool for VGI quality assessments that will be reported in later deliverables.

The research reported progressed much as planned but with additional quality assessments added in the light of broader changes to the subject. Specifically, the recent introduction of the General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR) has placed requirements on aspects of VGI data collection and use that had not been anticipated in the design of the LandSense project. Work to ensure that LandSense operates in a GDPR compliant way was undertaken to enhance the value of the tool.

The structure of the deliverable is as follows. Section 1 provides a brief summary of the QA service technical details. Section 2 describes data provided by each pilot and the analysis undertaken with the QA service. Section 3 highlights some brief conclusions and Section 4 lists recommendations for the next stage of work.

1 Introduction

In this document, we describe the preliminary analysis of data collected by the LandSense pilot projects. To achieve this, we use the LandSense QA-Platform, which comprises a Representational State Transfer (REST) Application Programming Interface (API) service architecture comprised of software components that undertake the data quality processing. Further technical details of the QA-Platform are described in Deliverable D5.3. As a summary, Figure 1 illustrates the software architecture of the system. The main service (denoted here as the QA-Platform server) includes a Java servlet-based framework based on an OpenAPI / Swagger implementation as an API. This system provides a simple deployment of REST endpoints for the QA processing. Following configuration, these endpoints expose QA functionality (which may be provided by different sub-systems or services) as a single interface point that can be interacted with using any REST client software.

The QA functionality provided behind the API endpoints may be a Java library or tool, R script or a remote HTTP service. In the case of R scripts, these are installed locally and are called from the QA-Platform using the RScript utility, which is part of the standard R distribution. To facilitate passing data between the two

systems, the R script is implemented so that it can be executed from a terminal, with the data and any parameters specified as arguments.

The LandSense GitHub repositories for the QA-Platform and QA R scripts are located at:

<https://github.com/LandSense/QA-Platform>

<https://github.com/LandSense/QA-R-Scripts>

Figure 1 Software architecture of the QA-Platform system.

2 Quality evaluation of data collected from the pilot projects

Organized within three themes, six LandSense pilot projects exist, with the data collected being subjected to quality analysis. QA tests among different pilots can be similar but may require individual tailoring. Table 2 shows the relevant quality checks for the pilot projects, which differ in terms of needs and data provided. These include the Urban Landscape Dynamics theme pilots of OSMLanduse validation of UHEI, UBA's CityOases app (former Frei.Raum.Netz) and IGN's IGN Mapper. The InoSens Crop Support pilot of the agricultural land use theme and the BLI Natura Alert app of the forest and habitat monitoring theme are also described. Amsterdam University's (VU) green spaces NL data were not ready for QA and so are omitted from this Deliverable. This section briefly reviews the needs of the LandSense pilots. Further details on data collection requirements and their relation to QA are given in Deliverable 5.2.

We describe seven QA analyses undertaken on the LandSense pilot data:

Polygon topology check identifies overlapping polygons in a set of polygon features. Specifically, the test returns the polygons that overlap and their number. Resolving topological issues is important, particularly if

area-based measures are to be calculated using citizen contributed data downstream of the QA service. This check was used as part of the InoSens Crop Support pilot where field boundaries were digitised.

Photo privacy check is currently applicable for the CityOases, Greenspaces NL, IGN Mapper and Natura Alert apps and is demonstrated within section 2.2.1. Image patterns that resemble human faces are identified and blurred using a pre-trained object detection model. Necessity for its mandatory application is given by EU GDPR legislation. A TensorFlow¹ based model was employed for the purpose of detecting faces. Further details on the implementation of the model (i.e., training images and network architecture) for achieving this are contained within the D5.3 report. The model was hosted as a separate web service and added into the QA-Platform REST interface using a remote HTTP service. This facilitates a convenient split as the face detection service is then decoupled from the rest of the QA-platform (at the expense of increased network traffic between the services), but can still be accessed via the same REST API as the other processing tasks.

Photo illumination check / photo blur check is required, and it is applied to the same apps/pilots as the previously mentioned photo privacy check, using similar technology. A lack of brightness or saturation of image content can render the captured photo as an obsolete image; metrics are used to judge its quality and may suggest a recapture (e.g., daylight images vs night images) or discard the photo. The blur check tool evaluates the degree of blurriness through analysing the result of applying a Laplace filter to the image (Pech-Pacheco et al. 2000). Specifically, blurriness is determined through convolving the image with a 3x3 Laplace kernel and calculating the variance on the resulting image. The decision on whether the image is blurry or not is determined according to whether the variance is above or below a user-parameterised threshold parameter. The COBWEB implementation of this tool documented a value of 1500 as a possible starting point for this. However, determining the appropriate threshold may be part-influenced by the use-case. Therefore, it is likely to be preferable to batch run the analysis across all images in order to understand the distribution of variance before selecting the hard threshold. To achieve this, the tool accepts a single image and returns a Boolean decision on whether the image is clear according to a variance threshold (sharpness indicator), and the actual variance value that was computed on the image.

Positional accuracy is applicable to all apps/pilots where GPS data are captured: Green spaces NL, CityOases, IGN Mapper, Crop Support and the Natura Alert app. For this report, positional accuracy has not yet been implemented. We define positional accuracy as the degree to which the digital representation of a real-world entity agrees with its true position on the Earth's surface (ISO 19157:2013). For LandSense, GPS accuracy and the estimated standard error are extracted from the contributor's data capture device, in this case a mobile phone. For guided campaigns (i.e., the contributor is directed to a point of interest), disparity between the point location and the contributor location is recorded, in addition to the standard GPS error. For instance, a GPS standard error of 20m and a disparity of 20m from the point of interest results in a total positional error of 40m.

Position offset is related to positional accuracy and is the spatial difference between multiple features belonging to the same spatial entity. For instance, for Crop Support, it is the difference between a digitized polygon from the web app and the GPS coordinates captured on the ground, where for the CityOasis app, it

¹ <https://www.tensorflow.org/>

is the offset between a guided location's point and the location where the data were captured. This QA test was not implemented in the current round of QA testing.

Categorical accuracy was applied to the apps/pilots: OSMLanduse validation (section 2.1), the application of the LandSense change detector service of IGN Mapper (section 2.3), and the deforestation monitor of the Natura Alert app (section 2.5). Although applicable, the Crop Support pilot was not yet accommodated for this QA check. Categorical accuracy is composed of overall accuracy and class specific user and producer accuracy.

As described in D5.1 and D5.2 following Olofsson et al. (2014), true marginal map proportions (Card 1982) were accommodated for the calculation of thematic accuracy measures (Congalton 1991). Sampling design followed Foody (2009). Sampling strategies varied across pilots and are described in detail in the respective sections.

Contributor agreement was applied to the apps/pilots as follows: OSMLanduse validation for the city of Geneva, where each location was visited exactly five times (section 2.1.2), CityOasis where a few locations were visited twice (section 2.2.3), and the IGN Mapper Change detector service validation of Toulouse, where the majority of points was visited twice (section 2.3.2). Contributor agreement is calculated using Scott's PI (Fleiss, 1971). For the interpretation of Scott's PI, kappa values ranging from 0 – 1 are used. Table 1 shows the categories of agreement levels of Scott's PI and the mode of interpretation. A high agreement of contributors on a certain response indicated high reliability of collected data, and thus that the citizen observation can be trusted. Within LandSense, any data collected in conjunction with contributor agreement was considered a reliable source of information or reference when a Scott's PI of at least 0.6 was achieved. In other words, 3 out of 5 contributors must agree on the category of the feature collected to make it count as valid.

Table 1 interpretation of Scott's PI (Sim and Wright, 2005)

Scotts PI (κ)	Interpretation
< 0	Poor agreement
0.01 – 0.20	Slight agreement
0.21 – 0.40	Fair agreement
0.41 – 0.60	Moderate agreement
0.61 – 0.80	Substantial agreement
0.81 – 1.00	Almost perfect agreement

Table 2 LandSense data quality analysis adapted from D5.2 Data Capture Requirements framework. "T" denotes a QA tested in this report. "A" denotes the test is applicable but not evaluated within this particular work. "-" denotes that the test is not applicable to the current pilot usage or the existing data captured by the pilot. * LandSense Change detector service involvement.

Theme	Urban landscape dynamics			Agricultural land use	Forest and habitat monitoring
Pilots / institutions	OSMlanduse validation / UHEI, CHEI	Greenspaces NL / VU, City Oases (formerly Frei.Raum.Netz) / UBA	IGN Mapper* / IGN	Crop Support / INOSENS	Natura Alert* app / BLI
Polygon topology check	-	-	-	T	-
Photo privacy check	-	T	A	A	A
Photo illumination check / photo blur check	-	T	A	T	A
Positional accuracy	-	A	A	A	A
Positional offset	-	A	-	A	-
Categorical accuracy	T	-	T	A	T
Contributor agreement	T	T	T	-	-

2.1 UHEI-OSMlanduse validation

The goal of this pilot is to validate osmlanduse.org to describe its suitability as a complementary land use product. The pilot was implemented for the cities of Heidelberg (Germany), Toulouse (France) and Vienna (Austria). These cities were chosen because they have good coverage of OpenStreetMap (OSM) data but differ in their urban characteristics, are part of CityOases (formerly called Frei.Raum.Netz), the IGN-France pilot (PAYSAGES) and the pilot for the City of Heidelberg itself. The cities vary in land use proportions and size from 109 km² for Heidelberg, 232 km² for Toulouse and 432 km² for Vienna. Osmlanduse.org is available worldwide, particularly with high detail for urban areas across Europe, and thus the pilot was applied for Geneva additionally. Related validation campaigns accommodated varying sampling populations.

The implementation of this pilot consisted of organizing three mapathons. These pilot specific validation campaigns occurred during an early stage of the LandSense project in June 2017 (validation mapathon during Heidelberg Land Use Mapathon) and January 2018 (Heidelberg Land Classification and Monitoring seminar) (subsection 2.1.1), and during the EUROGEOSS workshop in September 2018 in Geneva (subsection 2.1.2). To take bias introduced by individuals into account at a latter project stage (D5.2), additional data collection requirements were defined and implemented, including a measure to estimate uncertainties related to individual user contributions. For the Geneva mapathon, the new measure contributor agreement was introduced and implemented during the first LandSense extension campaign for osmlanduse.org land use validation of the Geneva municipality. There each reference point was interpreted by at least five different interpreters. The sampling strategy differed for Heidelberg, Toulouse, Vienna (Heidelberg mapathon, June 2017 and land classification and monitoring seminar January 2018) and the Geneva (EUROGEOSS workshop, September 2018) validation campaign.

Figure 2 outlines the data dependencies and process flow of the osmlanduse.org validation pilot; for 12 land use categories, categorical accuracy (overall accuracy, user accuracy and producer accuracy) and contributor agreement (Scott's PI) are calculated.

Figure 2 OSMlanduse (UHEI) pilot data dependencies and QA applications, *legend construction of land use is flexible; it is currently CORINE; ** Currently Landsat and Sentinel 2 are used; very high resolution (VHR) data are envisioned

2.1.1 Heidelberg, Toulouse and Vienna osmlanduse.org accuracies

During the validation campaigns (mapathons) in June 2017 and January 2018, a total of 4281 reference points were collected using laco-wiki.net with approximately 20 contributors. Table 3 shows sampling populations as proposed in D5.2. Recommendations on sampling design (Foody 2009) were accommodated as a starting point for sampling population and further populated with more samples to minimize class confidence interval (D5.2). Increasing sampling population was deemed appropriate to increase confidence (reduce confidence intervals, see plot whiskers of Figure 4) and narrow uncertainties.

Table 3 Class proportions and sampling population for Heidelberg pilot validation campaigns

	Heidelberg			Toulouse			Vienna		
	class proportions	estimated sampling population	final sampling population	class proportions	estimated sampling population	final sampling population	class proportions	estimated sampling population	final sampling population
1.1	0.17	149.80	196	0.17	155.42	358	0.39	256.67	338
1.2	0.04	40.24	287	0.06	60.89	626	0.21	177.22	433
1.3	0.00	4.88	9	0.01	9.15	10	0.00	3.17	23
1.4	0.04	38.96	14	0.07	69.24	51	0.05	48.59	186
2.0	0.28	243.83	372	0.40	297.74	81	0.21	186.53	399
3.0	0.46	280.51	562	0.26	222.53	111	0.11	114.64	121
5.0	0.01	15.46	42	0.03	30.00	8	0.03	29.88	54
Σ	1	773.68	1482	1	844.97	1245	1	816.70	1554

Figure 3 shows the locations of the reference points within the three osmlanduse.org products for classes urban fabric (1.1), industrial commercial and transport units (1.2), Mine, dump and construction sites (1.3), artificial non-agricultural vegetated areas (1.4), agricultural areas (2.0), forest and seminatural areas (3.0) and water bodies (5.0). Figure 3 show that the reference points for the osmlanduse.org pilot cities were sampled abundantly across the study sites. Sampling design ensured that each class received reference points.

Figure 3 Outline of reference points (sampling design) for osmlanduse.org (UHEI pilot) pilot cities H = Heidelberg, T = Toulouse and V = Vienna; *Artificial, non-agricultural vegetated areas

Figure 4 shows the results of the osmlanduse.org validation for the pilot cities of Heidelberg (H), Toulouse (T) and Vienna (V). The calculation of features followed the categorical accuracy quality check. Accuracies varied among the sites. Overall accuracy was highest for Heidelberg $87\% \pm 1.6\%$ where osmlanduse.org satisfies common mapping requirements (Anderson et al., 1976), followed by Vienna $62\% \pm 2.3\%$ and Toulouse $54\% \pm 2.7\%$ where osmlanduse.org currently does not accommodate mapping standards. Among the three

sites, class accuracy was consistently low for Mine, dump and construction sites (1.3) accompanied by large confidence intervals. The class itself covers the smallest fraction of all land use classes and should receive additional sampling in future efforts to narrow confidence intervals. Other class accuracies varied by site indicating that osmlanduse.org performance is dependent on location and thematic features. Urban fabric (1.1) producer's accuracy is consequently higher than user's accuracy across the three sites. Hence, urban fabric (1.1) is consequently overestimated in osmlanduse.org. In contrast, industrial, commercial and transport units (1.2) are underestimated rather than overestimated, except for Toulouse where user's and producer's accuracy for this class were similar. Artificial non-agricultural areas (1.4) performed similarly lower than Mine, dump and construction sites (1.3) except for Heidelberg. Accuracies for Agricultural areas (2.0), Forest and seminatural areas (3.0) and Water bodies (5.0) achieved low scores within Toulouse but are acceptable and often slightly overestimated for Heidelberg and Vienna.

Figure 4 Class accuracies and confidence intervals for UHEI pilot osmlanduse.org land use reference data consisting of 1482 samples for Heidelberg (H) overall accuracy 87%±1.6%, 1245 for Toulouse (T) overall accuracy 54%±2.7% and 1554 for Vienna (V) overall accuracy 62%±2.3%. *Artificial, non-agricultural vegetated areas

The difference in the class accuracies (area bias = user’s accuracy – producer’s accuracy) provides area bias as a measure of estimating class area accuracy. Positive area bias indicates that errors produced by underestimation are higher than by overestimation. Thus, an area bias close to 0, coupled with generally high (>85%) class accuracies and overall accuracy indicates that an estimation of area size is appropriate. Trends of specific land use prone to a certain area error become evident through this visualization.

Figure 5 displays the area bias of the respective land use maps and their classes. Area bias and confidence is especially large for the problematic class of Mine, dump and construction sites (1.3). In contrast, forest and seminatural areas (3.0) are characterised by only marginal area bias suggesting that area estimates are close to reality. Previous learning from Figure 4 for classes Urban fabric (1.1), where class area is consequently overestimated across sites and industrial, commercial and transport units (1.2) are underestimated (except for Toulouse), are evident. Agricultural areas (2.0) are generally overestimated, while water bodies (5.0) do not provide a conclusion about an overall common pattern.

Figure 5 Area bias of class accuracies for Heidelberg (H), Toulouse (T) and Vienna (V) *Artificial, non-agricultural vegetated areas. Positive area bias indicates that errors produced by overestimation are higher than by underestimation.

2.1.2 Geneva osmlanduse.org accuracy and contributor agreement

During the OSMLanduse.org validation campaign at EuroGEOSS September 2019 in Geneva, contributor agreement was introduced to improve confidence in the LandSense categorical accuracy by reducing contributor specific bias. In contrast to previous efforts, sampling populations were not considered due to the campaign format (limited time during workshop and limited contributors). Thus simple accuracy measures such as overall accuracy, user’s and producer’s accuracy without confidence interval nor true marginal map proportions were provided. The validation mapathon was limited to a time slot of 1.5h and 30 participants where a total of 150 reference points was interpreted at least 5 times resulting in a total of 750 interpretations. The Geneva validation was considered as a first experimental setup for this. Figure 6 shows all reference points determined by a random class proportional sampling design and Table 4 provides

statistics related to the figure. Out of the 150 reference points, 108 had a contributor agreement above 0.6 and thus qualified for use as reference points. Whenever contributor agreement was below 0.6, the majority rule for the reference point applied. The match of the map (osmlanduse.org) and the collected reference data are shown in the bottom left corner of Figure 6. The interpreted samples split up in almost perfect agreement (66 points) and substantial agreement (42 points). When those points collected by contributors with almost perfect agreement were compared with the osmlanduse.org product, an accuracy of 65% was reported. Points with high contributor agreement possess a high confidence in the interpretation. The lower the contributor agreement, the less reliable was the information provided by the individual contributor (i.e., the crowd). Table 4 shows that with decreasing contributor agreement, the estimates of mapping accuracy decline. Currently, contributor agreement consideration and campaign setups are still in a beta phase, with a full ramp up during 2019. However, the method provides an affordable, straightforward approach to estimate crowd performance.

Figure 6 Geneva validation campaign contributor agreement among 150 reference points, each inspected by 5 different interpreters; top facets show individual contributor agreement; bottom left indicates match of reference data (UHEI pilot) and osmlanduse.org and bottom right shows locations where osmlanduse.org agreed with the reference data and Scott's Pi was above 0.6 (i.e., substantial agreement).

Table 4 Frequency of Scott's PI for four different categories

Scott's PI	accuracy	sample count	validity
Almost perfect agreement (1 - 0.8)	65%	66	Valid > 0.6
Substantial agreement (0.8 - 0.6)	50%	42	108
Fair agreement (0.6 - 0.2)	39%	33	Not valid < 0.6
Slight agreement (0.2 - 0)	22%	9	42
Σ	-	150	

2.2 UBA - CityOases (formerly Frei.Raum.Netz)

The goal of this pilot is to understand citizen perception of green/open spaces for future municipality green space planning activities. Contributors are asked to visit locations, and at each location, to take pictures in different directions and answer a set of questions. The pilot data dependencies and the flow of data capture to create an emotional map of green spaces are depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7 CityOases (UBA) pilot data dependencies and QA applications

The City of Vienna CityOases guided campaign was implemented in 2018 and provided 256 contributions for which 27 observations were made by contributors. The data collected, illustrated in Figure 8, were comprised of:

- 256 guided point locations - Quest points
- 27 visited locations - Vienna test case points
- 135 images associated to test case points

Figure 8 CityOases guided campaign locations (Quest points) and visited locations (Vienna test case points). Base map copyright: 2018 Microsoft Corporation. 2018 Digital Globe CNES (2018). Distribution Airbus DS 2018.

2.2.1 Results of the face detection analysis

In the CityOases pilot, multiple photographs per visit point were collected. GDPR stipulates that images of individuals should not be stored by a digital service and thus such images should either not be recorded or should be processed to obfuscate faces. Figure 9 shows result of the face detection on two images collected by the pilot. The face detection service returns both an image annotated with detected faces, the number of faces detected in an image, the confidence scores associated with the detections and the bounding box pixel coordinates of the detection locations. Further processing is undertaken within the REST interface to produce a suitable image with the faces blurred based on the detected locations. Figure 10 shows the resulting image from blurring the locations identified by the face detection algorithm.

Figure 9 Example of user photographs from the CityOases pilot submitted and returned by face detection service.

Figure 10 Example of a user photograph from the CityOases pilot with blur applied to the face locations

2.2.2 Results of the photograph blur analysis

As part of the photograph analysis, the QA-Platform can be used to evaluate the images that have been collected by a mobile device. This can ensure that only photographs that are not blurred are hosted, or can be held back from being part of any further analysis or reporting. Figure 11 shows a sample image from the collected photograph set and its computed variance value.

Figure 11 Example image collected by the CityOases pilot (Laplace transform variance = 1420). This image does not score highly due to a relative lack of edges arising from the poor illumination.

Testing the above image (Figure 11), from its hosted location on Geo-Wiki, can be achieved with cURL:

```
curl -X POST "http://localhost:8080/wps-  
rest/service/thematicaccuracy/blurawtcheck?threshold=1500" -H "accept: application/json" -H  
"Authorization: Bearer secret-key" -H "Content-Type: application/json" -d "\"http://www.geo-  
wiki.org/assets/upload/201805/5af14ac4e39f5887439389.jpg\""
```

This returns:

```
{"isSharp":false,"variance":1420}
```

The same REST endpoint may be used to undertake batch processing of images through a basic script using cURL. For example, starting from a text file that lists the images and their location on a web server.

```
for i in $(cat vienna_testcase2_just_images.csv); do  
curl -X POST "http://localhost:8080/wps-  
rest/service/thematicaccuracy/blurawtcheck?threshold=1500" -H "accept: application/json" -H  
"Authorization: Bearer secret-key" -H "Content-Type: application/json" -d $i >> output.txt; done
```

A histogram of the Laplace transform variance (Figure 12) shows that the majority of images score above the default threshold of 1500. This indicates that the images are likely to have been collected using a sensible protocol as part of the data capture.

Figure 12 Histogram of the Laplace transform variance for 135 City Oases Vienna photographs.

2.2.3 Results of the contributor agreement

Contributor agreement was calculated for the points visited in Vienna. Due to the nature of attributes collected, only the category of “number of trees” for each reference point could be checked and the contributor agreement calculated. Figure 13 shows the number of visits for each point provided by the guided campaign. Most points were not visited, a few points were visited only once, and 5 points were

visited twice. For those points visited 5 times, contributor agreement was calculated for the category “number of trees”, and in each case, both contributors agreed on the number of trees.

Figure 13 Visited locations and count of revisit for UBA pilot

2.3 City of Toulouse – Land Use Change Validation

The goal of the Toulouse pilot is to enrich and update authoritative LULC data. Among the data collected during different campaigns, validation of changes detected by the LandSense Change Detection Service (CDS) is within the focus of this deliverable. The LandSense CDS was applied in Toulouse and its surroundings (17 000 km²) from April to September 2018 for detecting the occurrence of residential, industrial, infrastructure and other land use changes.

In total, 748 polygons were detected, representing changes from 2016 and 2018 (see Figure 14). This data set was sampled with 648 points, which were then validated during mapathons involving 60 contributors. Two orthophotos from 2016 and 2018 were used as base maps for validation. Contributors were asked to classify the point by choosing one value from a list of options: residential, industrial, infrastructure, no change. They also had the possibility to skip the point in case of doubt.

Figure 14. IGN Toulouse pilot data showing contributor validated points of change detected using the LACO-Wiki web-based tool. Base map copyright: 2018 French Geoportal

2.3.1 Results of the accuracy analysis

Among the total number of sampled points, 458 points were interpreted by two different contributors, allowing the calculation of contributor agreement. From this population, 57 points were removed, because they could not be interpreted by the contributors, leaving 401. Reference points were only considered valid whenever both contributors collecting the reference data agreed (Scott's PI value = 1), resulting in 224 valid reference points. A disagreement between contributors automatically resulted in the rejection of the reference point. Table 5 provides an overview of the agreement populations and the related accuracies for their respective fractions. Detailed class accuracy for the sampling population, where Scott's PI was appropriate (>0.6), is provided in Figure 15. Residential changes and industrial changes were underestimated; infrastructural changes and change to other lands was overestimated. Due to the large discrepancy in the user's and producer's accuracies, the mapping accuracy was low, particularly for infrastructure and other land. However, the user's accuracy for residential and industrial changes was satisfactory.

Table 5 Frequency of Scott's PI for four different categories in the IGN Toulouse campaign

Scotts PI	Accuracy	Sample count	Validity
Perfect agreement (1)	See Figure 15	224	valid
Poor agreement (0)	-	177	not valid
	-	401	

Figure 15 Class accuracies using reference data consisting of valid (224) samples for Toulouse, with an overall accuracy of 48% ± 5%.

The results for the remainder of the 190 reference points, which were interpreted once, are shown in Figure 16. In contrast to Figure 15, the confidence intervals shown in Figure 16 are larger. The confidence intervals of the class infrastructure (2) exceeded 100% and is not shown, thus rendering the use of the reference points as unusable and the performance poor.

Figure 16 Class accuracies for the land use reference data consisting of 190 samples for changes identified by the LandSense Change Detector Service (CDS) as of May 2018. The confidence intervals of the class infrastructure(2) exceeded the plotting margins and are thus not shown. The overall accuracy is 46% ± 10% ($\alpha = 0.95$).

2.3.2 Results of the contributor agreement

Figure 17 shows the locations of change that were produced by the LandSense CDS and the number of times they were visited by the contributors.

Figure 17 Locations of change and the number of times visited for the Toulouse pilot

Among the total sample data set, 458 points are validated by two contributors. Figure 18 illustrates the agreement between contributors.

Figure 18 The Toulouse validation campaign contributor agreement among 401 reference points, each inspected by 2 different interpreters; top two sub-figures show individual contributor agreement; bottom left indicates match of reference data and LandSense Change Detector Service; bottom right shows locations where the LandSense Change Detector Service agreed with the reference data and Scott's PI was above 0.8 (perfect agreement)

2.4 Serbia – CropSupport

The CropSupport case study focuses on the development of a spatially explicit crop rotation management system for farmers. The CropSupport case study collected field observations in the form of points denoting the mobile device GPS position of the user, ground-level photographs captured by the mobile device and web-digitised polygons of the field boundaries.

The data collected by the CropSupport case study (a sample of which is shown in Figure 19) were comprised of:

- 132 points
- 103 polygons
- 113 photographs.

Here, the quality of the polygons and photographs captured were analysed.

Figure 19 InoSens CropSupport pilot data consisting of user collected points based on mobile device position, digitised polygons of field boundaries, and land parcel boundaries. Base map copyright: 2018 Microsoft Corporation. 2018 Digital Globe CNES (2018). Distribution Airbus DS 2018.

2.4.1 Results of the photograph analysis

Batch analysis of the photograph blur, as described above in section 2.2.2, was undertaken to investigate the image quality. In general, a higher proportion of images were found to have blur or illumination issues. This may have been due to a poorer quality camera or less rigorous protocols during data capture.

Figure 20 and 21 illustrate examples of blurry images (low values for Laplace variance) evaluated with the photograph blur checking tool.

Analysing the variance values of all photographs (see Figure 22) allows identification of some unusual results. For example, one image results in a negative variance value of -8040. Investigation of this particular image, Figure 23, did not seem to highlight any obvious data quality issues relating to the image clarity. Therefore, further development and testing work is required to understand the conditions under which this result arises.

Figure 20 Example of CropSupport images evaluated with the photograph blur checking tool. Variance = 814 (left). Variance = 671 (right).

Figure 21 Example CropSupport images evaluated with the photograph blur checking tool. Variance = 7784 (left)

Figure 22 Histogram of the Laplace transform variance for 113 photographs

Figure 23 Example CropSupport image where Laplace transform variance is -8040.

Use of the photograph blur check identified several useful additions that could be made to the API implementation. Firstly, the API currently does not return any unique identifier within its results set. This

means that any client software written to interact with the API needs to be responsible for joining the results back to the input data, or it can be undertaken manually by a user.

2.4.2 Results of the polygon topology check

Among the 109 collected polygons, 9 were identified with overlap issues identified using the polygon topology check. Examples of these are shown in Figure 24.

Two minor technical issues were identified with the processing of polygons using the topology checker. The first concerned formation and parsing of the GeoJSON file format. Specifically, the tool was unable to parse the coordinate reference system (CRS) contained within the properties field of the CRS definition when it was formatted according to an OGC name (e.g. { "name": "urn:ogc:def:crs:OGC:1.3:CRS84" }). Altering the definition enabled it to be parsed correctly (e.g. { "name" : "CRS:84" } or { "name": "urn:ogc:def:crs:EPSG::4326" }). Further investigation into the cause is required to ascertain the solution, e.g., potentially updating the GeoTools Java library may solve it. A further issue was that slight geometrical changes were apparent in the returned set of polygons, when compared to the input. This was not evident when the input data were in projected coordinates (UTM), so may relate to the aforementioned CRS issue or may relate to the precision of the variables used by the tool being insufficient for geographic references.

Figure 24 Map of identified overlaps in InoSens CropSupport user polygons. Base map copyright: 2018 Microsoft Corporation. 2018 Digital Globe CNES (2018). Distribution Airbus DS 2018.

2.5 Spain and Indonesia - Natura Alert app

The pilot in Spain and Indonesia utilises the Natura Alert mobile app to report environmental disturbances. More precisely, contributors are asked to visit locations where recent deforestation (Indonesian island of Flores) are detected by the LandSense CDS. At the time of writing, the Natura Alert app was the only pilot utilising the LEP service for authorization and thus we include details demonstrating this integration in section 2.5.1. However, at the time of data analysis, the authorization and data service was in development and thus it was not adopted for the deforestation pilot described in section 2.5.3.

2.5.1 Authorization

The Birdlife demonstrator utilises the LandSense Authorization Service (AS). This means that in order for any QA to take place on data collected by the Birdlife app, an authorization procedure, called Oauth 2, is followed as described below:

- 1) LandSense AS application listing. This registers an application for using the authorization service (providing a *client_id* and *client_secret*).
- 2) Access token request. To allow query of the data associated with the application that has been registered on the AS, an access token must be requested from the LandSense AS. As a step in doing this, user credentials (e.g., EduGain, Google account, etc.) are provided and validated, with the AS providing an access token as a result.
- 3) The access token can then be used to interact with the data collected by the application defined in 1).
- 4) An updated access token can be requested following expiry of the token initially provided (e.g. after 29 minutes of inactivity).

Further details of the LandSense AS can be found in Deliverable 3.3.

2.5.2 Data - Query of Birdlife API using GraphQL

Once an access token has been acquired, it may be provided as part of a query to the BirdLife API. The BirdLife API has opted to use an implementation of GraphQL for interacting with the data storage. GraphQL is a relatively new language for an API, which allows the query to define the form of the fields that will be returned. This means the number of queries made over the network is minimised, and thus data transfer is more efficient.

An example of a GraphQL query for retrieving the data is:

```
query {  
  threats {  
    edges {  
      node {  
        id  
        longitude
```

```
    latitude
    type
    attachments {
      path
    }
  }
}
```

2.5.3 Reference data for deforestation alerts

Consistent and long-term medium resolution (10 – 60 m) monitoring capacities are required for accurate quantification of deforestation (Achard et al. 2016). The LandSense CDS is based on Sentinel 2 data, yet to date, no accurate Sentinel 2 deforestation detection method or framework exists. Sentinel 2 time series change detection remains a research topic due to the absence of historical data (e.g., +10 years of active data collection) in contrast to its recent launch (23.06.2015). Pre-processing pipelines do not support fully automated approaches in contrast to Landsat legacy and mature pre-processing.

As a result, reference data for the deforestation CDS is provided as part of the LandSense QA service. Figure 25 outlines the procedure applied to estimate annual spatially explicit deforestation for the Indonesian island of Flores from September 2016 to September 2018. All Landsat data covering Flores from the collection and level 1 Landsat archive, with a scene cloud cover below 30%, at Tier 1 Level 1TP surface reflectance normalized difference moisture index (NDMI) vegetation index (VI) were used. Pixels clear from clouds, shadows and other data contamination (data artefacts) were considered valid observations. Two additional processing rules were applied. First, only pixels that possessed a frequency of more than 30 (Devries et al., 2015) valid observations were considered for analysis, and secondly a forest mask was applied. The forest mask is a representation of forest cover as identified by Hansen et al. (2013) for the year 2016.

Figure 25 Overview of the processing steps related to deforestation alerts. *cc = cloud cover; **observation frequency >30 and application of a forest mask

For each valid observation, an irregular time series of NDMI values was created and tested for significant changes in the signal intensities through time. Breaks For Additive Season and Trend (BFAST) can account for seasonal variations (Verbesselt et al., 2010) where the adapted BFAST Monitor (Verbesselt et al., 2012) compares the tail of a time series against previous measurements. Such time series tails ranged from September 2016 (start of the LandSense project) onwards (i.e., the monitoring period). All previously captured data (historic period) were used to produce a historic model consisting of a trend and a harmonic component of the order of one. Monitoring period observations were compared against this model and their difference was the magnitude of the change. Significant offsets were described by breakpoints ranging throughout the monitoring period. Breakpoint absence was conformity of measured and modelled values. Because BFAST type models try to accommodate natural phenological variations, a detected breakpoint can be an identifier of irregular or potentially anthropogenic caused change. Land degradation of natural vegetated areas can be related to decreasing vegetation intensity. Hence, breakpoints characterized by a negative magnitude were considered for further analysis.

BFAST Monitor outputs the change date and the magnitude of change (deviation of measured change and expected intensity). Binary generalized linear models (GLM) were employed to determine those magnitudes related to deforestation (Devries et al., 2015; Schultz et al., 2016). In total, 571 reference points were randomly spread into areas represented by negative magnitudes to determine suitable magnitude thresholds for deforestation for each tile (Figure 26). As suggested in D5.2, the sampling design was determined according to Foody (2009) and the accuracy assessment uses standard accuracy measures (Congalton, 1991, p. 199) following best practices (Olofsson et al., 2014) inducing true marginal map proportions (Card, 1982). Figure 26 shows the areas of deforestation detected by the CDS (in red) along with deforestation patterns for selected areas.

GLM	Position/ number of calibration samples
	Path 111 row 66 / 80
	Path 112 row 66 / 122
	Path 113 row 66 / 42

Figure 26 Binary generalized linear models and the identification of the magnitude thresholds for deforestation detection based on 571 reference points (Devries et al., 2015; Schultz et al., 2018)

Figure 27 Red areas show hot spots of detected deforestation. Sub-figures A-F show deforestation patterns at a pixel level

2.5.4 Results of the accuracy analysis

The results of the accuracy assessment are shown in Figure 28. Deforestation was detected with relatively high producer accuracy ranging from 52% to 85%, and user accuracy ranging from 88% to 98%. In particular, the bulk of changes in the centre of the Island were detected with high accuracy. The deforestation pattern is characterized by deforestation occurrence close to non-forested areas, suggesting agricultural expansion and charcoal production as a deforestation driver.

Figure 28 Estimated deforestation detection accuracy based on 571 reference points for each tile; whiskers show confidence interval based on Card (1982)

3 Conclusions

This preliminary analysis indicated that useful insights can be made on the quality of VGI in the context of Earth Observation and citizen science scenarios. The testing highlighted some small technical issues in deploying particular pieces of data processing functionality and minor potential improvements to the API interfaces, which can be fixed in further versions of the service. The ongoing development of the pilots will also lead to additional and better-defined requirements on the tool implementations and for new QA tests. Furthermore, in order to arrive at a greater number of novel scientific experiments that can demonstrate the value of citizen-contributed data, larger samples of such data may be required.

4 Recommendations

To date, the data collected for some of the pilots are limited or are effectively test data created by the developers of the tool. LandSense partners should be encouraged to generate larger real-world data sets for further evaluation of the QA service. Moreover, LandSense partners should be encouraged to provide feedback on the QA tools, i.e., what they like and dislike, and new features or analyses to consider. The

publically accessible version of the QA service (currently hosted by Sinergise) should be updated in order demonstrate the latest features.

5 References

- Achard et al 2016 - http://www.gofcgold.wur.nl/redd/sourcebook/GOFC-GOLD_Sourcebook.pdf
- Anderson, J., Hardy, E., Roach, J., Witmer, R., 1976. A Land Use and Land Cover Classification System For Use With Remote Sensor Data. US Geol. Surv. Prof. Pap. - Wash. DC 964.
- Antoniou, V. and Skopeliti, A., 2015. Measures and indicators of VGI quality: An overview. *ISPRS annals of the photogrammetry, remote sensing and spatial information sciences*, 2, p.345.
- Card, D., 1982. Using known map category marginal frequencies to improve estimates of thematic map accuracy. *Photogrammetric Engineering and Remote Sensing*. 48, 431–439.
- Congalton, R.G., 1991. A review of assessing the accuracy of classifications of remotely sensed data. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 37, 35–46. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0034-4257\(91\)90048-B](https://doi.org/10.1016/0034-4257(91)90048-B)
- Devries, B., Verbesselt, J., Kooistra, L., Herold, M., 2015. Robust Monitoring of Small-Scale Forest Disturbances in a Tropical Montane Forest Using Landsat Time Series. *Remote Sens. Environ.*
- Fonte, C.C., Bastin, L., Foody, G., Kellenberger, T., Kerle, N., Mooney, P., Olteanu-Raimond, A.M. and See, L., 2015. VGI quality control. *ISPRS Annals of Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, 2, pp.317-324.
- Goodchild, M.F. and Li, L., 2012. Assuring the quality of volunteered geographic information. *Spatial statistics*, 1, pp.110-120.
- Foody, G.M., 2009. Sample size determination for image classification accuracy assessment and comparison. *Int. J. Remote Sens.* 30, 5273–5291. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431160903130937>
- Hansen, M.C., Potapov, P.V., Moore, R., Hancher, M., Turubanova, S.A., Tyukavina, A., Thau, D., Stehman, S.V., Goetz, S.J., Loveland, T.R., Kommareddy, A., Egorov, A., Chini, L., Justice, C.O., Townshend, J.R.G., 2013. High-Resolution Global Maps of 21st-Century Forest Cover Change. *Science* 342, 850–853. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1244693>
- Olofsson, P., Foody, G.M., Herold, M., Stehman, S.V., Woodcock, C.E., Wulder, M.A., 2014. Good practices for estimating area and assessing accuracy of land change. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 148, 42–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2014.02.015>
- Pech-Pacheco, J. L. Cristobal, G. Chamorro-Martinez, J. and Fernandez-Valdivia, J. 2000. Diatom autofocusing in brightfield microscopy: a comparative study. In: *Proceedings 15th International Conference on Pattern Recognition. ICPR-2000, Barcelona, Spain, 2000*, pp. 314-317 vol.3. doi: 10.1109/ICPR.2000.903548
- Schultz, M., Shapiro, A., Clevers, J., Beech, C., Herold, M., 2018. Forest cover and vegetation degradation detection in the Kavango Zambezi Transfrontier Conservation Area using BFAST Monitor. *Remote Sens.* 10, 1850.

- Schultz, M., Clevers, J., Carter, S., Verbesselt, J., Avitabile, V., Vu Quang, Hien, 2016. Performance of vegetation indices from Landsat time series in deforestation monitoring. *Int. J. Appl. Earth Obs. Geoinformation* 52, 318–327.
- Sim, J., Wright, C.C., 2005. The kappa statistic in reliability studies: use, interpretation, and sample size requirements. *Phys. Ther.* 85, 257–268.
- Senaratne, H., Mobasher, A., Ali, A.L., Capineri, C. and Haklay, M., 2017. A review of volunteered geographic information quality assessment methods. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 31(1), pp.139-167.
- Verbesselt, J., Hyndman, R., Newnham, G., Culvenor, D., 2010. Detecting trend and seasonal changes in satellite image time series. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 114, 106–115.
- Verbesselt, J., Zeileis, A., Herold, M., 2012. Near real-time disturbance detection using satellite image time series. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 123, 98–108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2012.02.022>